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PUBLIC REGULATION OF SMALL BUSINESSES DEVELOPMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF THE ODESA REGION'S TERRITORIAL COMMUNITIES RESTORATION

ДЕРЖАВНЕ РЕГУЛЮВАННЯ РОЗВИТКУ МАЛИХ ПІДПРИЄМСТВ У КОНТЕКСТІ ВІДНОВЛЕННЯ ТЕРИТОРІАЛЬНИХ ГРОМАД ОДЕСЬКОЇ ОБЛАСТІ

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Шепель М.Є. Державне регулювання розвитку малих підприємств у контексті відновлення територіальних громад Одеської області. Оглядова стаття.

Сьогодні складно передбачити, яким чином малі підприємства будуть функціонувати у повоєнний час. Таким чином, державне регулювання та підтримка малого підприємництва у післявоєнний період стає надзвичайно важливим питанням. Метою статті виступило запропонувати шляхи удосконалення державного регулювання розвитку малих підприємств у контексті відновлення територіальних громад Одеської області. Авторкою зроблено аналіз науково-дослідної літератури з теми, зроблено SWOT-аналіз розвитку малих приватних підприємств в Одеській області. Запропоновано шляхи удосконалення державного регулювання розвитку малих підприємств у вигляді моделі. Дана модель включає наступні компоненти створення інфраструктури підтримки малих підприємств; спрощення адміністративних процедур, фінансова підтримка, освіта та підготовка, розвиток підприємницької етики та культури, партнерство з місцевими органами влади та громадськими організаціями, стимулювання інновацій та технологічного розвитку.

Ключові слова: державне регулювання, малі підприємства, територіальні громади, Одеська область

Shepel M.Ye. Public Regulation of Small Businesses Development in the Context of the Odesa Region's Territorial Communities Restoration. Review article.

To date it is difficult to predict how small businesses will function in the post-war period. Thus, public regulation and support for small businesses in the post-war period becomes an extremely important issue. The article aims to propose the ways to improve public regulation of small businesses development in the context of the Odesa region's territorial communities recovery. The author analyzes the research literature on the topic, makes a SWOT analysis of the Odesa region's small businesses development. The ways for improving public regulation of small businesses development in the form of a model are proposed. The model includes the following components such as creating a small businesses support infrastructure; administrative procedures simplification; financial support; education and training; entrepreneurial ethics and culture development; partnership with local authorities and NGOs; stimulation of innovation and technological development.

Keywords: public regulation, small businesses, territorial communities, the Odesa region

The Russian Federation's full-scale military aggression against Ukraine has fundamentally changed all areas of life. This invasion has had serious consequences for many economic entities and institutions that determine the country's livelihood. The military aggression has also affected small businesses, which are an integral part of the country's economic system. After the outbreak of a full-scale invasion in Ukraine, small businesses found themselves in a difficult situation, although they were able to respond to new unforeseen challenges more quickly and flexibly than large corporations. As a result of the war, small businesses were forced to relocate. According to official data, the largest relocation areas were relatively calm regions of Ukraine: Lviv (24%), Zakarpattia (14.5%), Chernivtsi (9.8%), Ivano-Frankivsk (8.3%), Khmelnytskyi (7.3%), and Ternopil (6.3%) [1]. As of June 2022, about 7.8% of businesses had relocated abroad, and 4.1% had completely relocated [2].

Even in the face of a large-scale invasion, Ukrainians have not stopped starting new businesses. For example, 198,011 small private companies were founded in 2022 (including 152,468 during the full-scale invasion), and 304,048 in 2023 [3, 4]. As of March 2022, Ukrainians registered 1,946 small private enterprises, and in September 2023, this number increased to 35,587 [4].

Today, it is difficult to predict how small businesses will function in the post-war period. Therefore, public regulation and support of small businesses in the post-war period is becoming an urgent issue.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Various scholars delved into the challenges of managing businesses and fostering entrepreneurship, and assessing their competitiveness. G. Mazur, A. Rudenko, S. Filypova, R. Levkina, Y. Kotko, S. Pysarenko, M. Hrytsayenko, Z. Shatska, Y. Gorbachev, I. Sydoruk, V. Atiukshyna, A. Butenko, Y. Prodius, O. Rozhok, L. Chernysheva, I. Nazarke-

vych, O. Nazarkevych, V. Antoshchuk, N. Paryeva contributed to this discourse. Similarly, enterprise security and inclusive social responsibility were studied by O. Sorokivska, I. Hnatenko, G. Smokvina, O. Yankovska, N. Bondarchuk, A. Pedko, O. Prodius, M. Dudek, I. Bashynska, S. Filyppova, S. Yermak, D. Sichon, and M. Hrytsayenko. Marketing practices within businesses were explored by Z. Sokolovska, N. Yatsenko, M. Fedorova, H. Temchenko, O. Bondarchuk, K. Astafieva, N. Pavlishyna, V. Rezantseva, O. Vashkiv, Yu. Gavrylenko, A. Kramarenko, M. Vyshnevskaya, L. Donets, O. Nikoluk, and R. Znachkek. The trajectory of business development in Ukraine was investigated by V. Marchenko, D. Kharytonenko, L. Symkiv, S. Pobihun, A. Bezus, K. Shafranov, and others. Additionally, the challenges and opportunities of ICT utilization in entrepreneurship were addressed by scholars such as E. Abu-Shanab, M. Osmani, B. Soga, S. Vyas-Dogapersad, D. Vianna Thompson, R.T. Rust, J. Roda, P. Wilde, I. Merrell, J. Phillipson, M. Gorton, P. Covey, P. Budania, G. Garvita, G. Lodha, S. Budauria, B. Sinf, E. Rao, M. Sira, P. Sharma, C. Sharma, S. Schögl, C. Postulka, R. Bernstein, and C. Ploder. Moreover, the significance of small businesses in community development was analyzed by researchers including B. Burkinsky, I. Kuprianchik, A. Dorosh, V. Saliuta, O. Kovbasa, T. Ilchenko, I. Zastrozhnikova, R. Korinets, and H. Pererva, among others.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

However, the main aspects of public regulation of small businesses require further research and improvement.

The aim of the article is to propose the ways for improving public regulation of small businesses development in the context of the Odesa region's territorial communities recovery.

The main part

Small businesses in developed countries perform important economic functions that are often overlooked by large corporations. They provide an inflow of material, financial, natural, information and human resources to the economy. It allows large companies to get rid of unprofitable operations, regulates supply and demand in the market, controls the level of product prices, creates additional jobs and deals with the problem of hidden unemployment. Reducing property inequality and improving living standards also help to decrease social tensions in society. The advantage of small businesses is their ability to quickly adapt to changes in the market, find niches in production and services, respond to consumer demands, and effectively introduce new products. They also tend to constantly increase their production and service volumes, which allows them to remain competitive and grow. In addition, small businesses provide greater efficiency of capital investment in production, both in terms of the amount of funds and the time of their return, and they have the lowest investment needs among all business entities [5].

When studying small businesses activities, the scholars came to the following conclusions.

Kh. Kaidrovych notes that, depending on their financial capabilities and competencies, small businesses cannot always compete with their more powerful competitors using the latest methods. However, they are successfully engaged in those sectors of the domestic economy where the use of resources of large businesses is not efficient. Additionally, sometimes some of the small businesses can unite their efforts and turn into medium or even large business entities [6].

V. Gryga, S. Bogdan and N. Isakova conducted a study that examined the factors that influence small businesses efficiency, in particular, their interaction with large companies and the level of innovation in their activities. Based on the analysis results of empirical data obtained in the course of the managers' survey of the small businesses in the Chernihiv region, it was found that technological innovations, in particular, the introduction of new materials, technologies, packaging and product design, have the greatest impact on profits. It is also noted that organizational innovations do not directly affect the profitability of enterprises. In addition, the study confirmed that the interaction between small and large businesses in Ukraine has a positive impact on the economic activity of small enterprises [7].

The researchers from the State Organization "Institute of Market and Economic&Ecological Researches of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine", such as A. Butenko, N. Shlafman [8, 9], and D. Isachenko [10], conducted the study to quantify the small businesses development and noted a high level of regional diversity in its development in favour of the most prosperous and economically successful regions of the country.

B. Burkinsky identified the goals of supporting small businesses at the regional level, such as increasing the volume of products, jobs, and services provided by small businesses, increasing the small businesses contribution to GRP, increasing the share of small businesses in total industrial production, supporting small businesses in priority sectors for the region, such as high value-added manufacturing, import substitution, export production, and increasing the small businesses investment activity [11].

Exploring the role of small businesses in the territorial communities' economic and social development, V. Mitsa argues that small businesses play a crucial role in the economic system of the community. The importance is determined by the fact that in developed countries at least one in six households owns such a business. Small businesses employ local citizens, which contributes to the improvement of the economic situation in the community [12].

T. Kuklinova shares the same opinion, noting that small businesses play an important social role, providing self-employment, a good social environment, forming a vital level of income, promoting employees' initiative and entrepreneurship, activating the processes of initial capital accumulation for further development, which is of great importance both in wartime and in the post-war period [13].

Thus, public regulation of small businesses development is becoming increasingly important in the context of the territorial communities post-war recovery.

Public regulation of entrepreneurial activity should be understood as the objectivity realization of the economic need to coordinate and harmonize the business structures activities to achieve the overall goal of macroeconomic development, i.e. meeting social needs. Thus, the achievement of this goal largely depends on the existence of a management system, forms and methods of public regulation of entrepreneurial activity [14].

V. Dykan and O. Shramenko note that SMEs are characterized by independent management, dynamic development, and a significant role in creating jobs in the country. They ensure high efficiency of capital investments, create a competitive environment, saturate the market with goods and services, and increase tax revenues to the budget. The scholars believe that the main strategic direction of public regulation of SMEs should be the formation of public-private partnerships. This partnership is seen as the most advanced method of regulation in the post-industrial economic development. They emphasize that such a partnership is an optimal and effective form of management that will contribute to solving strategically important tasks of the country's economic development [15].

In the process of Ukraine's economic recovery, supporting small businesses in the regions is gaining urgency. It is important to restore small businesses in local communities, which will create new jobs and help Ukrainian veterans adapt to social life.

In order to identify the ways to improve the public regulation of small businesses development in the context of the territorial communities restoration in the Odesa region, it is necessary to conduct a SWOT analysis of the prospects for small businesses. This SWOT analysis can help identify the key factors that influence the small businesses development in the Odesa region and identify areas for further actions and strategies.

The strengths include geographical location (the Odesa region is located in the south-west of Ukraine, near the Black sea, which creates favourable conditions for tourism and maritime business development); local government support (local authorities can provide support to small businesses via funding programmes, training and consultancy); industry (the presence of industrial zones and enterprises can provide opportunities for partnerships and supply); active entrepreneurial environment (the presence of active entrepreneurs in the region).

The weaknesses include corruption and bureaucracy (corruption problems and complexity of administrative procedures may make it difficult to start and grow a business); low economic activity (some areas of the Odesa region may have low levels of economic activity, which may be an obstacle to business development); uneven level of development (differences in the level of development between urban and rural areas may create inequalities in access to resources and support).

The opportunities include tourism development (tourism development in the Odesa region could become a source of income for small hospitality and service businesses); agricultural sector (large agricultural potential could provide opportunities for the agricultural enterprises and agribusiness development); transport infrastructure (transport infrastructure development could stimulate logistics and transport enterprises in the region).

The threats include economic instability (unstable economic situation in the country may affect consumerism and demand for goods and services of small businesses); competition (increased competition in the region may reduce margins and profitability for small businesses); political instability (political conflicts and instability may become an obstacle to business development and investment in the region); military aggression by the Russian Federation (damage to infrastructure and logistics routes).

For greater clarity, let us present a SWOT analysis of the of small businesses development in Table 1.

Table 1. SWOT analysis of the development of small private enterprises in Odesa region

Strengths	Weaknesses
Geographical location Support from local authorities Industry outlet Active business environment	Corruption and bureaucracy Low economic activity Unequal level of development
Features.	Threats
Tourism development Development of the agricultural sector Development of transport infrastructure	Economic instability Competition Political instability Military operations

Source: the author's own elaboration

In the course of the joint study between Odesa Polytechnic and the University of Portsmouth (UK) within the framework of the Twinning Grant Scheme (Project UUT25 "The Mechanisms of Small Business Development in the Context of Ensuring National Security and Post-War Restoration of Territorial

Community of Ukraine") [16], the following factors were identified that would hinder the small businesses development in the territorial community in the post-war period high rates of local taxes (46.4%); insufficient financial resources (54.1%); unavailability of credit funds (24.6%); bureaucratic obstacles

(47.3%); low solvency of buyers (52.2%); difficulty connecting to engineering networks (16.9%); absence of sewage treatment facilities (10.1%); low qualification of employees and the possibility of their arrangement (29%); lack of the necessary number of qualified employees (38.2%); excessive pressure on

the business from the control bodies (35.3%); poor transport accessibility to major markets/consumers (19.8%); public resistance to the enterprise development (4.3%); change in the market market situation (23.7%); the limited opportunity to expand production premises (18.8%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Factors that will hinder the development of small business in the territorial community in the post-war period
 Source: compiled by authors on materials [16]

It is important to develop the ways to improve public regulation of small businesses development in the context of the Odesa region's territorial

communities restoration . Let us present the ways for improving public regulation of small businesses development in the form of a model (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The Model for Improving Public Regulation of Small Businesses Development in the Context of the Odesa Region's Territorial Communities Restoration
 Source: the author's own elaboration

The aim of the model is to improve public regulation of small businesses development in the context of the Odesa region's territorial communities restoration. The result is the improved public regulation of the of existing small businesses activities and the opening of new ones in the Odesa region's communities.

Let us consider the proposed model in more detail. Creating an infrastructure to support small businesses, i.e. the infrastructure development such as business incubators, small business support centres, and business accelerators, can provide small businesses with access to resources, education, and mentoring.

Administrative procedures simplification, i.e. reducing bureaucracy and simplifying business registration procedures, can help small businesses develop. This may include introducing electronic services and online consultation mechanisms for entrepreneurs.

Financial support includes providing access to finance for small enterprises through credit

programmes, grants or other financial tools that can stimulate their development. Local financial instruments development, such as microcredit, can also be helpful.

Education and training mean that education and training programmes for small entrepreneurs should be developed to help them acquire the necessary skills to successfully manage their businesses. This may include financial literacy, marketing, resource management and other key aspects.

For example, a joint study between Odesa Polytechnic and the University of Portsmouth (UK) within the framework of the Twinning Grant Scheme (Project UUT25 "The Mechanisms of Small Business Development in the Context of Ensuring National Security and Post-War Restoration of Territorial Community of Ukraine") [16] found that 61.5% of the respondents would like to take a course to improve their entrepreneurial skills, 23.4% were undecided (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Training to improve entrepreneurial skills

Source: compiled by the author based on [16]

Among the proposed topics, the respondents chose the most relevant ones: Finance Management (59.9%); Entrepreneurship Fundamentals (40.8%); Human

Resources Management (48.7%); Economic Analysis (48.7%); Procurement Management (40.1%); Image and Ethics in Managerial Activity (41.4%) (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. The most relevant topics for small entrepreneurs' competencies development

Source: compiled by the author based on [16]

Entrepreneurial ethics and culture development. Creating a favourable entrepreneurial culture that mentions achievements and success, and encourages innovation can stimulate small businesses development. This can be done through measures to promote entrepreneurship and the creation of networks

for the experience exchange. Business ethics is also of great importance. Business ethics in Ukraine is studied in the context of the current political, economic and social situation. It is a unique combination of three factors: the old communist mentality, the new "mafia" capitalism and Ukrainian nationalism have created a

situation where the application of internationally accepted ethical concepts may not lead to success [17] In the context of the Russian Federation’s war against Ukraine, business decisions to stay or to completely abandon operations in the Russian Federation involve a variety of legal, commercial, reputational, ethical and logistical considerations. The OECD’s Responsible Business Conduct (RBC) standards are expected to set expectations for how businesses should prevent and address the negative impacts of their operations and supply chains on people, the planet and society, and contribute to sustainable development in the countries where they operate. RBC can help inform how companies respond to war, including human rights and

integrity risks in their supply chains. This will be relevant both within the region and globally as supply chains change in some cases. RBC can manage and enable businesses to remain in Ukraine responsibly to preserve jobs, economic activity and essential goods for Ukraine, given the context of extreme stress in which Ukrainian workers and supply chains operate [18].

A joint study between Odesa Polytechnic and the University of Portsmouth (UK) within the framework of the Twinning Grant Scheme (Project UUT25) found that 70.5% of respondents indicated that soft skills are essential for small businesses development (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. The Need for Soft Skills for Small Businesses Development
Source: compiled by the author based on [16]

The respondents who took part in the survey indicated the following soft skills: communication skills (68.3%); emotions regulation (41.5%); critical

thinking (65.9%); conflict resolution skills (64%); leadership skills (53.7%); team management skills (60.4%); time management skills (48.2%) (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Soft Skills for Small Entrepreneurs
Source: compiled by the author based on [16]

Partnership with local authorities and civil society organizations. Cooperation between government agencies, local communities and NGOs can help solve problems and provide support for the small businesses development.

A joint study between Odesa Polytechnic and the University of Portsmouth (UK) within the framework of the Twinning Grant Scheme (Project UUT25 “The Mechanisms of Small Business Development in the Context of Ensuring National Security and Post-War

Restoration of Territorial Community of Ukraine”) revealed that small businesses expect the following support from the government: financial support (60.5%); creating business support infrastructure (Business Support Centers) (38%); The business promotion (popularization) (33.7%); consulting services provision (consultations, meetings, etc.) (26.3%); Information services Provision (informing, newsletters, etc.) (23.8%); The company will not need any support (20%) (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Support for Small Business Development from the State/City Authorities/Community

Source: compiled by the author based on [16]

Stimulating innovation and technological development, including support for innovative and technological start-ups through funding programmes, incubation centres and access to scientific and technological capacity, can stimulate the development of small businesses in the region.

We believe that the proposed ways for improving public regulation of small businesses development will help to restore territorial communities in the Odesa region in the post-war period.

Conclusion

Today it is difficult to predict how small businesses will operate in the post-war period. As the Ukrainian economy recovers, support for SMEs in the regions is gaining importance. It is important to restore small businesses in territorial communities, which, on the one hand, will provide new jobs and, on the other hand, will help Ukrainian veterans adapt to social life. To identify the ways to improve public regulation of small business development in the context of territorial

communities restoration in the Odesa region, a STEM analysis of the prospects for small businesses was conducted. This SWOT analysis can help identify the key factors that influence the development of small private entrepreneurship in the Odesa region and identify areas for further actions and strategies. The ways to improve public regulation of small business development in the context of territorial communities restoration in the Odesa region are given in the model. The outcome is the improvement of the work of existing and the opening of new small small businesses in the Odesa region's communities. The model has the following components: creation of a small business support infrastructure; simplification of administrative procedures; financial support; education and training; development of entrepreneurial ethics and culture; partnership with local authorities and NGOs; and stimulation of innovation and technological development. The etiquette of using social media for small businesses in territorial communities needs further study.

Abstract

The Russian Federation's large-scale military aggression against Ukraine has fundamentally changed all the areas of life. This invasion has had serious consequences for many economic entities and institutions that determine the country's viability. The military aggression also affected small businesses, which are integral to the country's economic system. After the outbreak of a full-scale war in Ukraine, small businesses found themselves in a difficult situation, although they could respond to new unforeseen challenges more quickly and flexibly than large corporations. As a result of the war, small businesses were forced to relocate. According to official data, the largest relocation areas were relatively calm regions of Ukraine: the Lviv region (24%), the Transcarpathian region (14.5%), the Chernivtsi region (9.8%), the Ivano-Frankivsk region (8.3%), the Khmelnytskyi region (7.3%), and the Ternopil region (6.3%). As of June 2022, about 7.8% of businesses had relocated abroad, and 4.1% had completely relocated.

Even in the face of a large-scale invasion, Ukrainians have not stopped starting new businesses. Thus, in 2022, 198,011 small private companies were founded (including 152,468 during the full-scale invasion), and in 2023 - 304,048. In March 2022, Ukrainians registered 1,946 small businesses, and in September 2023, this number increased to 35,587.

To date, it is difficult to predict how small businesses will operate in the post-war period. As Ukraine's economy recovers, support for SMEs in the regions is gaining importance. It is important to restore small businesses in territorial communities, which, on the one hand, will provide new jobs and, on the other hand, will facilitate Ukrainian veterans's adaptation to social life. The aim of the article is to propose ways to improve public regulation of small business development in the context of the Odesa region's territorial communities restoration.

In order to identify the ways for improving the public regulation of small businesses development in the context of the territorial communities restoration in the Odessa region, a SWOT analysis of the prospects of small entrepreneurship was conducted. This SWOT analysis can help identify the key factors that influence small businesses development in the Odessa region and identify areas for further actions and strategies. The ways to develop small businesses in the form of a model aimed at improving public regulation of small businesses development in the context of territorial communities restoration in Odessa region are given. The result is the improvement of the existing small businesses activities and the launching of new ones in the Odessa region's communities. The model has the following components: creating a small businesses support infrastructure; administrative procedures simplification; financial support; education and training; entrepreneurial ethics and culture development; partnership with local authorities and NGOs; and stimulation of innovation and technological development. The etiquette of using social media for small businesses in territorial communities needs further study.

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